

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN AN EFFORT TO INCREASE COMPETITIVENESS AT MTsN - (DESCRIPTIVE STUDY AT MTsN 1 WEST KOTAWARINGIN REGENCY AND MTsN 1 PALANGKA RAYA CITY, CENTRAL KALIMANTAN PROVINCE)

MULYONO ¹, ADE TUTTY R. ROSA ², WASKA WARTA ³ and AGUS MULYANTO ⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Universitas Islam Nusantara, Bandung, Indonesia.

Email: ¹mulyono@uninus.ac.id , ²adetuttyrosa@uninus.ac.id , ³waskawarta@uninus.ac.id,

⁴agusmulyanto@uninus.ac.id

Abstract

The problem of Madrasah strategic management in an effort to increase competitiveness lies not only in the managerial abilities of the madrasa head himself, maximum participation from teachers and students, as well as the involvement of parents and the community, but also the lack of optimal image branding efforts carried out by the Madrasah. This research aims to describe and analyze environmental analysis, formulation, implementation and evaluation of madrasah strategic management in an effort to increase competitiveness. This research uses a qualitative approach with descriptive methods. The results of this research found: (1) the environmental analysis carried out by the madrasah was prepared based on the principles of environmental analysis. (2) The strategic formulation in an effort to increase the competitiveness of MTsN at these two MTs is in accordance with the concept using SWOT analysis. (3) Strategic implementation at these two MTs has implemented the principles of strategic management evaluation. (4) Strategic evaluation in an effort to increase competitiveness has been carried out based on madrasah self-evaluation. In general, this research also concluded that strategic management has been implemented based on strategic management principles, although it has not been supported by complete data so that the institution's goals have not been achieved holistically.

Keywords: Strategic Management and Competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Today's society is increasingly realizing that education is one way to change human nature into a true human being, because knowledgeable humans are of course not the same as those without knowledge. Education is the most important thing in life and is expected to always develop. Education in general is a life process in developing each individual to be able to live and live (Rosyadi et al., 2023). In general, the condition of madrasahs is seen from the learning facilities, the condition of the quality of educators and education personnel and the condition of financing (Afizialhaq & Sirojuddin, 2022). The poor condition of madrasahs results in the competitiveness of madrasahs being weak and receiving less public attention compared to public schools (Bahri, 2023). To achieve excellence in terms of competitiveness, MTsN can apply a strategic management approach as one of a series of processes for establishing blueprints and plans to determine the various things needed to achieve the goals of an organization (Meutia, 2021). The scope of strategic planning can begin with establishing a philosophy so that it can be known what strategies and methods are needed to realize the desired goals (Zaid, 2021). So there is a need for good strategic management.

Strategic management is a set of managerial decisions and actions that determine a company's performance in the long term, which includes: environmental mapping (both external and internal), formulating or developing strategies (long-term strategy or planning), implementing strategies, and evaluating and controlling (Adnan et al., 2022). According to (Rahman et al., 2021) competitiveness in general is the concept of strategic management, seen from the process of environmental analysis, strategic planning, evaluation and control. States that. Thoughts about the strategic management approach were also expressed by (Luciano et al., 2020) stating that; 'Strategic management is large-scale and long-term planning so that organizations can interact effectively in production and optimize the achievement of both strategic and operational goals'. (Bozarth & Chapman, 1996) , reveals that the field of strategic management presents many rich and useful avenues for conducting research.

The strategy has the fact of combining many theoretical perspectives and covering many diverse topics allowing for tremendous variations in its implementation in educational institutions (Madrigal et al., 2013). The implementation of strategic management at for-profit institutions has demonstrated the organization's success in achieving competitive advantage (Erniati Siregar, 2020). Strategic management is a multidimensional concept that has been widely used and applied in all fields of education (Suresmi et al., 2022). Strategic management is the ongoing implementation of planning, monitoring, analysis and evaluation of all the needs required by an organization in an effort to achieve its goals (Kuthambalayan & Bera, 2020). Changes that occur quickly and spontaneously in the organizational environment will require organizations that are able to continuously evaluate strategies (Tabroni et al., 2023). Implementation of strategic management helps organizations know the condition of the organization (Rijal et al., 2022). Strategic management is always something that must be formulated, implemented and also evaluated in order to achieve the goals of educational institutions (Kamal et al., 2023). Strategic management is also an important tool for competitiveness between institutions, but what is also in line with strategic is maintaining the performance that has been achieved because maintaining the quality that has been achieved will be very difficult compared to achieving it (Rofiaty, 2019).

Strategic management in its implementation brings various benefits to educational institutions, apart from being able to help MTsN managers achieve their goals, it can also create innovation in order to increase competitiveness, this condition is strengthened by the opinion of (Sari et al., 2023). Educational institutions need to implement strategic plans, requiring commitment from management, consistency, and support from human resources, technology, infrastructure, and adequate investment costs (Olhager, 2003). Based on preliminary studies carried out, currently many schools/madrasahs are in decline due to not maximizing their strategic management so that the goals they want to achieve always do not meet the targets, there are even schools that only use Strategic Plans (strategic plans) as documents to fulfill accreditation but do not carry them out properly. So that there is no improvement in terms of quality or infrastructure so that the school's competitiveness decreases. Madrasah competitiveness is the ability of a madrasah education unit to carry out certain actions or efforts in order to improve the quality of its education so that it is superior and able to compete with other educational units of the same level (Wu et al., 2023). Increasing the competitiveness of educational

institutions must be a top priority for institutional managers, especially nowadays with the growth of many new institutions that offer advantages that attract public interest with quality programs with various innovations and creativity in their human resources (Riinawati, 2022). This kind of thing will be of concern to the people who have always wanted quality education for their sons and daughters, so it is hoped that after leaving the institution there will be changes, both physically, spiritually and religiously (Pujianti & Sarpendi, 2022).

One strategy to increase the competitiveness of madrasas is the implementation of strategic management (Hariyanto et al., 2021). This concept emphasizes the madrasah's efforts to identify what it wants to achieve, and how it should achieve valuable results within the scope of education, so that the madrasah can understand its competitive strengths and develop sustainable competitive advantages systematically and consistently (Suwandi & Fitri, 2023). One of the real challenges for madrasas in the modern era is building the competitiveness of madrasas (Widjaja et al., 2022). High competitiveness will place madrasas as institutions of choice while making a greater contribution to the spread of religion and advancing national education (Meredith & Akinc, 2007). According to (Olhager & Prajogo, 2012), competitiveness includes:

- (1) The ability to strengthen one's market position,
- (2) The ability to connect with the environment,
- (3) The ability to improve performance without stopping, and
- (4) The ability to uphold a profitable position.

The results of observations carried out by researchers at several state and private MTs in West Kotawaringin Regency and MTs in the Palangka Raya City area show several problems, including sports fields and sports equipment not being available for the number of students, and library facilities and desks not being well maintained. chairs for reading for students are still limited in number with limited space and the available books are incomplete and poorly maintained, the number of toilets for students is still insufficient, storage space for goods or warehouses does not meet safety requirements and is not equipped with shelves or cupboards, learning media is still limited, especially electronic media such as LCDs and learning media are not updated and are not well maintained so that teachers still tend to lecture, laboratory space is available but the equipment and materials Facilities and infrastructure that are complete and in accordance with students' needs can foster motivation because using teaching aids or learning media will attract students' attention so that students will be more enthusiastic in participating in the learning process and encourage students to achieve high learning achievements (ref). Based on a preliminary study conducted at MTs Negeri 1 Kotawaringin Barat Regency and MTs Negeri 1 Palangka Raya City, the educational facilities and infrastructure are very adequate, but there are still several learning facilities that are inadequate, including learning resources, learning facilities in the classroom such as the availability of LCD, as well as the existence of learning governance that truly serves student education. Based on the background above regarding strategic management in an effort to increase the competitiveness of MTsN, various problems can be identified including: MTsN strategic

management has not been optimally implemented at the MTsN level so that these conditions make MTs not optimal in meeting community expectations. This is partly due to governance, ability and teacher competency is still not optimal, plus institutional resources are not yet sufficient to increase the competitiveness of MTs. MTsN's competitiveness is still faced with various obstacles, including insufficiently competent teaching and education staff resources, inadequate infrastructure, and still constraints in terms of financing. This research aims to describe and analyze the strategic environment, strategic formulation, strategic implementation and strategic evaluation in an effort to increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

RESEARCH METHODS

Descriptive research is a research method that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon being studied. So this research method's main focus is to explain the research object. So that it answers what events or phenomena occur in terms of strategic environmental analysis, formulation, strategy, strategic implementation and strategic evaluation in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City. The results describe the research object in detail. As a method that attempts to provide long and detailed explanations and analysis, the descriptive method has several advantages including:

- 1) Being able to analyze problems or problems that are difficult or cannot be measured numerically;
- 2) Able to make observations in natural and natural social contexts;
- 3) Has the potential to combine qualitative and quantitative research .

Research Sites

The choice of MTs Negeri 1 Kotawaringin Barat Regency and MTs Negeri 1 Kota Palangka Raya was based on several reasons, MTs Negeri 1 Kotawaringin Barat Regency is an MTsN located in the central government of Pangkalan Bun City with the number of students in the 2023-2024 academic year totaling 661 students consisting of classes VII = 224 students, class VIII = 221 students and class IX = 216 students. Meanwhile, according to the data on New Student Admissions in 2022-2023, there were 257 people and 224 students were accepted. In the 2023-2-24 academic year, there were 252 new student admissions and 224 were accepted, with 7 groups available. The number of people interested in MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat has increased every year, but space availability is still limited. Meanwhile, MTs Negeri 1 Palangka Raya City is located in the urban center of the capital of Central Kalimantan Province. In the 2023-2024 academic year, it has 809 students. There are 336 male students and 473 female students. Data on the number of new student admissions in the 2022-2023 academic year was 267 students, and increased in the PPDB for the 2023-2024 academic year by 288 students with a group size of 9 for class VII students. With the data above, it is a logical reason to make MTsN the locus of research by looking at data on the number of enthusiasts at the two MTsN.

Research Subjects

Research subjects or research respondents were selected purposively, that is, the informants selected were people who had sufficient knowledge and experience related to the research problem. According to the words used, an informant is a person who has information about the subject that the researcher wants to know. So informants can be grouped based on the problem formulation and research focus. If you are able to obtain key informants, the researcher may only need to use one person, but if not, he may have to have a number of informants to support each other. It needs to be emphasized that there is no standard benchmark for how many informants are needed in a qualitative study, the benchmark is the information itself: how far the available information can answer the study question or problem. The key informants in this research are:

- a) Head of Madrasah Education, Office of the Ministry of Religion, West Kotawaringin Regency and Palangka Raya City.
- b) Head of MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City
- c) Deputy Head of MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City
- d) Teacher Council of MTsN1 West Kotawaringin and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City (D4).

All of the subjects above were determined by the researcher as informants who could provide information about

- 1) Strategic environmental analysis in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City;
- 2) Strategic formulation in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City;
- 3) Strategic implementation in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City; and
- 4) Strategic evaluation in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City

Data Collection Techniques

Based on the source of data collection, in this research the researcher used primary data, namely data obtained directly from the object under study through data collection procedures and techniques in the form of observation, interviews and document studies which were specifically designed according to the researcher's objectives. The data collection techniques in this research include observation, interviews and document study:

a. Interviews

Interviews are a form of non-test type evaluation media and are carried out through conversation and questions and answers. Apart from field observations, researchers also used interview methods for data collection. In this research, the data collection method carried out

through interviews is intended to reveal data, namely

- 1) Strategic environmental analysis in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City;
- 2) Strategic formulation of the quality of education services at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City;
- 3) Strategic implementation in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City; and
- 4) Strategic evaluation in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

Meanwhile, interviews were conducted by researchers with previously determined respondents, namely:

- 1) Head of Madrasah Education, Office of the Ministry of Religion, West Kotawaringin Regency and Palangka Raya City (A1);
- 2) Head of MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City (B2);
- 3) Deputy Head of MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City (C3); and
- 4) Teacher Council of MTsN1 West Kotawaringin and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City (D4).

The purpose of interviews is to obtain direct information about certain situations and conditions, complete a scientific investigation, and obtain data to influence certain situations or parties.

b. Observations

An important aim of conducting observations is to provide researchers with a realistic picture of a behavior or event related to the activities of the research object. Apart from collecting data, observations are carried out with the aim of obtaining a conclusion about the object being observed. Observation also aims to describe an object and everything related to the object being studied. The researcher carries out participant observation, that is, the researcher will be involved with the activities of the subject being observed or used as a source of research data. The observations carried out were related to collecting related data in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat and MTsN 1 Kota Palangka Raya .

c. Documentation

Documentation study or what is usually called document study is a data collection technique that is not directly aimed at research subjects in order to obtain information related to the research object. In documentation studies, researchers usually search for historical data on research objects and see to what extent the ongoing processes have been well documented. Methods or document studies, although initially rarely considered in qualitative research methodology, have now become an important and inseparable part of qualitative research methodology. This is due to the new awareness and understanding that is developing among

researchers, that a lot of data is stored in the form of documents and artifacts. Documentation study is a data collection technique by studying documents to obtain data or information related to the problem being studied. Document studies in this research include:

- 1) MTsN strategic plan and objectives documents;
- 2) Education service administration
- 3) Assessment system
- 4) Document 1 and MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat and MTsN 1 Kota Palangka Raya documents .

Data Collection Instruments

No	Research purposes	Research Indicators	Data sources	Research Techniques		
				W	O	DS
1	Environmental Analysis	<p>a. Internal Environmental Analysis , including:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Organizational structure; 2) Organizational culture, 3) MTsN organizational resources <p>b. Environmental Analysis External , including:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) government policy 2) Sociocultural society 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, West Kotawaringin Regency and Palangka Raya City 2) Head of MTsN 3) Deputy Chief of MTsN 4) MTsN Teachers Council 	√	-	√
2	Strategic Formulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Development of vision and mission and long-term goals b. Formulation of goals; c. Strategic formulation d. Determination of appropriate strategic policies to be applied 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, West Kotawaringin Regency and Palangka Raya City b. Head of MTsN c. Deputy Chief of MTsN d. MTsN Teachers Council 	√	-	√
3	Strategic Implementation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Implementation of strategic programs 2) Support the program implementation budget a. Standard operating procedures 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, West Kotawaringin Regency and Palangka Raya City b. Head of MTsN c. Deputy Chief of MTsN d. MTsN Teachers Council 	√	√	√
4	Strategic Evaluation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Reassess external and internal factors 2) Measuring performance 3) Take corrective action 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion b. Head of MTsN c. Deputy Chief of MTsN d. MTsN Teachers Council 	√	√	√

Note: (W) Interview, (O) Observation, (DS) Documentation Study

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency

a. Strategic environmental management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency.

Based on the results of interviews and document studies that have been carried out, several key factors can be identified as solutions for madrasas in an effort to increase the competitiveness of MTsN MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat. The madrasa organizational structure has been carefully formulated, emphasizing integration, strong leadership, and effective communication between staff and decision makers. This factor allows madrasas to respond quickly to changes in the educational environment and ensure that every element of the organization supports the madrasah's vision and mission. Apart from that, in formulating the organizational structure, the madrasah also pays attention to the skills and roles of each staff, so that their duties and responsibilities are in line with the goals of MTsN. Clear thinking in terms of divisions, strategic planning, effective supervision and continuous training for staff have made a significant contribution in optimizing available resources and achieving the set competitiveness objectives.

Quality human resource management, internal policies that support innovation, and support for sustainability are also important elements in the strategy to increase madrasah competitiveness. The results of the interviews revealed that government policies related to accreditation, evaluation, curriculum innovation and sustainability practices also had a positive impact in supporting efforts to increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat. All these factors, together with a supportive organizational culture, create a strong foundation for these madrasas to continue to increase their competitiveness and provide quality education.

Based on the results of interviews and document studies, the organizational culture of MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat plays a very important role in supporting efforts to increase the competitiveness of madrasas. In interviews with madrasas, the organizational culture at MTsN 1 was found to be very supportive of efforts to increase competitiveness. They encourage collaboration, innovation, and providing constructive feedback as key elements in madrasah organizational culture. This factor contributes positively by providing positive encouragement for all madrasa staff, ensuring that each team member feels they are contributing to achieving common goals. An organizational culture that supports collaboration, innovation and constructive communication is a valuable asset in efforts to increase madrasah competitiveness. From the results of this interview, it can be concluded that the madrasa has succeeded in creating an environment that encourages active participation and creative contributions from all madrasa staff. This culture provides a strong foundation in achieving the goal of increasing the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat.

Based on the results of interviews and document studies that have been carried out, it can be identified that organizational resources play a key role in efforts to increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat. Adequate physical facilities, modern teaching and learning equipment, and wise financial management are key elements that contribute to increasing the

competitiveness of madrasahs. All these resources have been allocated effectively in accordance with the educational needs and strategic planning of the madrasah.

Apart from that, human resources also play an important role in supporting increasing the competitiveness of MTsN. Highly qualified and committed teaching staff, as well as a rigorous selection and development process, ensure that the madrasah has a team of experienced educators capable of providing quality education. Student involvement, parental support, and active participation in the community are also factors that strengthen madrasah competitiveness. From the results of this interview, it appears that MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat has succeeded in utilizing resources, both physical and human, optimally in an effort to achieve the goal of increasing madrasah competitiveness.

b. Strategic formulation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency

Strategic management is a process or series of fundamental and comprehensive decision-making activities, accompanied by determining how to implement them, which are made by the leadership and implemented by all levels within an organization, to achieve goals. Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies that have been carried out, the development of the vision and mission as well as long-term goals of MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin were revealed as key steps in efforts to increase the competitiveness of madrasahs. In interviews with madrasah officials, it was revealed that developing the madrasah's vision and mission was a very important first step. The MTsN team involves various stakeholders, including staff, students and parents in this process, so that the resulting vision and mission reflect shared aspirations and goals. A strong vision is the main guide in achieving excellence in education, and the long-term goals that have been set become a roadmap that provides direction for every madrasah action and program. From the results of this interview, it appears that developing a vision and mission as well as long-term goals is a strategic foundation that supports efforts to increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat. This is a valuable first step in creating a shared vision for a better future in education.

Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies that have been carried out, the development of objectives in an effort to increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat is proven to be a collaborative process that is structured and centered on real needs. The madrasah team conducted a thorough evaluation of current conditions and identified areas that needed improvement. The results of this evaluation become the basis for formulating specific and measurable goals. In addition, the goal development process involves input from all staff and related parties. This involvement ensures that the goals set reflect a shared vision and commitment to increasing the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat. In practice, madrasahs continually monitor and evaluate progress towards these goals and, if necessary, make strategic adjustments to remain relevant in the face of a dynamically changing educational environment. From the results of this interview, it appears that the process of developing goals is a fundamental step in efforts to increase madrasah competitiveness.

c. Strategic implementation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency.

Strategic implementation is an important step in the strategic planning process. It involves converting strategic plans, which include the long-term goals of the organization, into concrete actions to achieve desired results. Strategic implementation is a series of activities in which strategic plans are executed and converted into measurable performance in an organization. Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies that have been carried out, the process of implementing strategic programs to increase competitiveness can be explained in detail. These strategic programs are implemented through close cooperation from all madrasa staff, who collaborate to achieve common goals. To ensure the success of strategic programs, each program has detailed planning, including clear implementation stages, appointment of responsible persons, and continuous performance measurement. Monitoring and evaluation play an important role in ensuring that these programs are in line with the long-term goals that have been set and can evaluate the impact of each program.

In addition, involving active participation from students and parents is a strategy adopted to support programs to increase competitiveness. This includes providing students with additional training and character development projects. The madrasa also establishes partnerships with educational institutions and related organizations to support the implementation of these strategic programs. From the results of this interview, it appears that the focus on collaboration and active participation from all stakeholders has had a positive impact on efforts to increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat. Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies that have been carried out, budget and financing support plays a key role in efforts to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat. The budget allocation for education at MTsN is very carefully considered, and efforts are made to ensure that the available funds are sufficient to support strategic programs aimed at increasing the competitiveness of madrasas.

Apart from relying on routine budgets, madrasahs also actively seek additional sources, such as grants and sponsorships, to support special initiatives. In this case, collaboration with external parties, such as non-governmental organizations or private parties, becomes important. Madrasas strive to maintain efficiency and transparency in budget management, so that available funds can be allocated wisely for strategic programs that support increased competitiveness. From the results of this interview, it appears that good budget support and efficient fund management efforts are important factors in the success of strategic programs to increase competitiveness.

d. Strategic evaluation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency.

Strategy evaluation is the final stage in strategic management. Managers really need to know when certain strategies are not working well. Strategy evaluation is the main tool for obtaining this information. This can be done by assessing or carrying out a strategy evaluation process. As one of the management functions, supervision is the final action carried out by managers in

an organization. Evaluation is the process of observing or monitoring the implementation of organizational activities to ensure that all work being carried out runs according to a predetermined plan. Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies, we can illustrate that the evaluation of external and internal factors plays a central role in the strategy to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat. This evaluation process is carried out periodically to understand environmental changes and their impact on efforts to increase madrasah competitiveness.

A SWOT analysis, which includes identification of new opportunities, possible threats, as well as an in-depth understanding of the madrasah's strengths and weaknesses, is used as a framework to carry out this evaluation. Thus, this evaluation process helps MTsN 1 to evaluate and adjust the strategies that have been previously formulated. This makes MTsN 1 an entity that is responsive to changes in the educational environment and is committed to continuing to improve its competitiveness.

Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies, it can be stated that the measurement of competitive performance at MTsN 1 Kotawaringin Barat was carried out comprehensively and systematically. This madrasah utilizes the indicators set out in the strategic plan as the main guide in measuring its competitive performance. Performance measurement covers several aspects, including student academic achievement, student participation in extracurricular activities, as well as feedback obtained from parents and students. These data are used to evaluate the success of strategic programs that have been formulated. In addition, there is internal monitoring carried out periodically to measure the performance of madrasa staff. This includes assessing professional development, teaching quality, and staff contributions to achieving madrasah competitiveness goals. A holistic approach in performance measurement provides a strong foundation for MTsN 1 to continue to improve efforts to increase competitiveness in accordance with the organization's vision and mission.

2. MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City

a. Strategic environmental management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

In the current era of globalization and information, the external and internal environment has become a force that greatly influences organizations. Rapid technological advances have caused the madrasah environment to change rapidly and become increasingly complex. This is an important issue for the management of the organization. Madrasah managers find it more difficult to predict the future (because of uncertainty), more difficult to make the necessary plans and strategies for their madrasahs. In addition, they have great difficulty in understanding gray events, which makes it difficult to make appropriate decisions.

Based on the results of interviews and document studies, it can be concluded that the madrasa organizational structure is a key element in efforts to increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City. The madrasa organizational structure was formulated with the main aim of optimizing the potential of the madrasa and achieving higher competitiveness. This is done

through the formation of units and departments that suit the needs of the madrasah, as well as through a clear division of tasks for staff and teachers. This organizational structure is not only an administrative framework, but also a means of facilitating efficient coordination between all madrasa elements. In this structure, decision making can take place more quickly and precisely, provide better responsiveness to environmental changes, and provide strict monitoring of the implementation of strategic programs that support madrasah competitiveness. Thus, a well-planned and organized madrasah organizational structure can be a strong foundation for developing and improving the competitiveness of MTsN in a sustainable manner.

Based on the results of interviews and document studies, it can be stated that organizational culture at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City has a significant role in supporting efforts to increase the competitiveness of madrasahs. This organizational culture forms a strong foundation for achieving these goals. MTsN promotes an inclusive culture, which provides space for all madrasa members to participate and contribute according to their respective talents and expertise. Apart from that, teamwork is a value that is highly valued in the MTsN organizational culture. Harmony and collaboration between staff and teachers is the key to implementing strategic programs that support madrasah competitiveness. A culture of innovation is also an important aspect, encouraging initiatives that stimulate creativity and improve the quality of education. This creates a dynamic environment that is ready to face changes and challenges in the world of education with careful and appropriate solutions. High commitment to quality educational services is the main pillar in MTsN's organizational culture. Consistent support for efforts to improve the quality of education provides a solid foundation for the competitiveness of madrasahs in facing increasingly fierce competition in the world of education

b. Strategic formulation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies, the process of developing the vision, mission and long-term goals of MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City in an effort to increase competitiveness is a step that involves various stakeholders. Active participation from teachers, staff, students, school committees and the surrounding community is at the core of this process. A collaborative and inclusive approach allows various views and aspirations to be respected and integrated in the madrasah's vision and mission documents. The resulting vision inspires the entire educational community with a clear and desirable picture of the future, while the mission reflects a commitment to achieving the main goals of madrasa education. In addition, the long-term goals formulated take into account student needs, educational developments, and challenges faced in the educational environment, ensuring that every step taken supports the achievement of strategic goals that will increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

Through this participatory process, the vision, mission and long-term goals of MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City not only become a formal document, but also become a guide that moves the entire educational community in achieving madrasa success in increasing competitiveness at the national level. Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies, it was revealed that the process of formulating goals in an effort to increase the competitiveness

of MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City was a collaborative effort involving various stakeholders. Teachers, administrative staff, school committees and the community are an integral part of this process. In formulating goals, the approach applied is to create goals that are specific, measurable, realistic, and closely related to the madrasah's vision and mission. These goals are designed to serve as clear guidelines for achieving better competitiveness. This process not only creates measurable and targeted goals, but also ensures that these goals are in line with previously formulated strategies. Thus, the formulation of mature objectives is an important first step in supporting strategic steps in order to increase the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

c. Strategic implementation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies, the implementation of the strategic program to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City involves a series of organized steps. First of all, the madrasah forms a team or working group consisting of various stakeholders, such as teachers, administrative staff and relevant parties. This team has the main responsibility for designing a detailed action plan, including setting concrete achievement targets and scheduling appropriate time. These strategic programs include developing a superior and relevant curriculum, increasing teacher qualifications, as well as various other initiatives that significantly contribute to increasing the competitiveness of madrasas.

Apart from that, the interview results revealed that the madrasah was also actively seeking input from various related parties in the process of formulating this strategic program. This reflects their commitment to ensuring that the programs implemented truly meet the needs and challenges faced by these madrasas in an effort to increase competitiveness. An in-depth understanding of the madrasah environment, both from an internal and external perspective, has become an important basis in directing the strategic steps taken. Thus, this participatory and data-based approach is a key factor that supports success in increasing the competitiveness of MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

In this context, it is important to note that this strategic program is the basis for responding to the challenges faced by madrasas in facing changing times. The implementation of these programs is also clear evidence of MTsN 1's seriousness in improving the quality of education and its competitiveness, in line with the aim of analyzing and understanding strategic management in an effort to increase competitiveness in this educational institution.

d. Strategic evaluation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City. / Strategic evaluation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies, it appears that the madrasah has a proactive approach in reassessing the external and internal factors that have been formulated in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City. This evaluation process includes routine environmental analysis. For external factors, the madrasah

closely monitors developments in education policy, trends in the world of education, as well as changes in the education market that may affect the madrasah. Meanwhile, the interview results also revealed that internal factors, such as staff and teacher performance, curriculum development, and management effectiveness, are evaluated regularly. This evaluation provides important insight to the madrasah about the extent to which these internal factors have supported or may need to be adjusted to existing strategies. Understanding how the madrasah actively assesses and responds to changes in external and internal factors is an important aspect in analyzing strategic management to increase competitiveness in the madrasah.

This ongoing evaluation process reflects the madrasah's commitment to remaining relevant in facing the dynamics of the ever-changing educational environment. Based on the results of interviews, observations and document studies, it was revealed that measuring competitive performance at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City is a crucial aspect in their strategic management efforts. The madrasah carries out this performance measurement process carefully, by collecting and analyzing relevant data.

The data that is the focus of performance measurement involves a number of important indicators, such as student exam results, graduation rates, student attendance, and the level of satisfaction of parents and students with the educational services provided by madrasahs. Apart from that, the interview results also show that performance measurement involves evaluating the performance of teachers and madrasah staff as well as monitoring related to progress in implementing strategic programs. The results of this measurement are used as a basis for assessing the extent to which the madrasah has achieved the competitiveness goals that have been set. Understanding how this performance measurement is implemented is an important element in analyzing strategic management to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

DISCUSSION

a. Strategic environmental management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City./ Strategic environmental management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

The importance of organizational structure in increasing the competitiveness of madrasahs is manifested in the description of the division of tasks of MTsN elements. Madrasah heads in carrying out their duties function and act as educators, managers, administrators, supervisors, leaders, innovators and motivators.

In detail, the duties and roles of madrasah heads in efforts to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City are as follows;

- 1) The head of the madrasah as an educator The head of the madrasah as an educator is tasked with carrying out the teaching and learning process effectively and efficiently.

- 2) The head of the madrasah as manager has the following duties:
 - (1) Develop plans;
 - (2) Organizing activities;
 - (3) Directing activities;
 - (4) Coordinating activities;
 - (5) Carry out supervision;
 - (6) Evaluating activities;
 - (7) Determining policy;
 - (8) Hold meetings;
 - (9) Making decisions;
 - (10) Managing the teaching and learning process;
 - (11) Prepare RAPBM (Madrasah Revenue and Expenditure Budget Plan);
 - (12) Regulate administration, students, personnel, facilities and infrastructure;
 - (13) Organize Student Organizations (If any);
 - (14) Regulate madrasah relations with the community and related agencies.
- 3) The head of the madrasah as administrator, is tasked with carrying out administration: planning; organizing; briefing; coordinating; supervision; curriculum; studentship; administration; office personnel, finance; library; laboratory; skills/arts room; counseling guidance; school health efforts (UKS); student organizations; joint learning resource center (PSBB).
- 4) The head of the madrasah as supervisor is tasked with carrying out supervision regarding: The teaching and learning process; Guidance and counseling activities; Extracurricular activities; Administrative activities; Collaborative activities with the community and related agencies; Facilities and infrastructure; and 6 K Activities.
- 5) Madrasah principal as leader: Can be trusted, honest and responsible, understands the conditions of teachers, employees and students. Having a vision and understanding the mission of the madrasah, making decisions about internal and external affairs of the madrasah, creating, searching for and selecting new ideas.
- 6) Madrasah Heads as Innovators: carry out reforms in the fields of teaching and learning, guidance and counseling, extra-curricular activities and procurement, carry out teacher and employee development, carry out reforms in exploring funding sources in the madrasah committee and the community.

7) The madrasa head as a motivator: Arranging an office space that is conducive to work, arranging a classroom that is conducive to teaching and counseling, arranging a laboratory space that is conducive to practicum, arranging a library space that is conducive to studying. Arranging a cool and orderly madrasah courtyard/environment, creating harmonious working relationships between teachers and employees. Creating a harmonious working relationship between the madrasah and the environment, applying the principles of reward and punishment. In carrying out his duties, the head of the madrasah can delegate to the deputy head of the madrasah.

b. Strategic formulation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City

One of the real challenges for madrasahs in the modern era is to build madrasah competitiveness. High competitiveness will position madrasahs as institutions of choice while making a greater contribution to the spread of religion and advancing national education. This was emphasized by Sumihardjo (2008) who stated that competitiveness includes:

- (1) the ability to strengthen one's market position,
- (2) the ability to connect with the environment,
- (3) the ability to improve performance without stopping, and
- (4) the ability to uphold a profitable position.

The ability to strengthen its market position is interpreted as the madrasah's existence as the madrasah of choice that has the ideal number of students with the supporting capacity and infrastructure that the madrasah has. At least the number of students is stable and increases along with the amount of carrying capacity they have.

Strengthening the position of madrasahs as the madrasahs of choice is very important considering the increasingly competitive nature of education in the regions along with the establishment of many private schools and the increasing capacity of state schools.

Currently, madrasahs can be likened to ships in the middle of the ocean, so the head of the madrasah as captain must be able to map out alternative routes with a non-linear thinking framework. A suitable strategy is needed to be used in the worst situations and conditions so that the trip is smooth and comfortable.

Madrasah must also have high adaptability to their environment so that their existence is not like being in a vacuum but has a relationship with the surrounding environment. Madrasah relationships can take the form of relationships with the business/industrial world, universities, related institutions (School Security Police (PKS), Scouts, PMI, or other government organizations at the city/district level), village governments, and other parties who have the same vision as madrasahs.

c. Strategic implementation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

The strategic formulation process in the context of increasing the competitiveness of MTsN is the core of comprehensive strategic management. Madrasahs need to have a clear vision of their long-term goals to achieve better competitiveness. This strategic formulation process involves identifying problems, opportunities, strengths and weaknesses of the madrasah. With a strong understanding of internal and external conditions, madrasahs can formulate appropriate strategies to overcome obstacles, take advantage of opportunities and maximize their advantages.

In strategic formulation, madrasahs must consider various aspects that can support the achievement of competitiveness goals. This includes academic aspects, teacher qualifications, resources, management, and community participation. Strategic formulation must include specific and measurable action plans, as well as determining concrete steps that must be taken. Therefore, a deep understanding of how strategic formulation can combine these various aspects is important in strategic management analysis in increasing the competitiveness of MTsN.

It is important to remember that the strategic formulation process must be continuous and responsive. Changes in the educational environment and the development of madrasahs themselves require regular strategy updates. Regarding how madrasahs can carry out a dynamic strategic formulation process, enabling them to remain relevant and competitive in the long term. Seriousness and commitment in the strategic formulation process are the main factors in achieving the goal of better competitiveness at MTsN. With a deep understanding of the role of strategy in increasing madrasah competitiveness, it will be seen how a strategic management approach is one of the keys to success.

d. Strategic evaluation management in an effort to increase competitiveness at MTsN 1 West Kotawaringin Regency and MTsN 1 Palangka Raya City.

Strategic evaluation in increasing the competitiveness of MTsN plays a central role in understanding the environment and internal weaknesses that affect madrasahs. In this effort, MTsN regularly evaluates external factors that influence the educational environment, such as changes in educational policies, educational trends, and educational market dynamics. SWOT analysis is used as a tool to identify opportunities, threats, strengths and weaknesses of madrasahs. Meanwhile, internal factors related to madrasah performance are also routinely evaluated. This includes staff and teacher performance, curriculum development, and management effectiveness. This internal evaluation provides important insight into the extent to which these factors have supported or may need to be adapted to existing strategies.

This strategic evaluation process is very important because it helps MTsN to assess the extent to which the madrasah has achieved the competitiveness goals that have been set. External evaluation helps to respond to changes in the educational environment, while internal evaluation helps evaluate the internal quality and effectiveness of the madrasah. Thus, strategic evaluation provides a strong basis for determining the steps needed to increase the

competitiveness of MTsN. In conclusion, a comprehensive strategic evaluation, involving analysis of external and internal factors, is an integral part of strategic management in increasing the competitiveness of MTsN. An in-depth understanding of how this strategic evaluation process is implemented and contributes to the formulation and implementation of effective strategies will be the focus of this research. This continuous evaluation reflects MTsN's commitment to remaining relevant and adaptive in facing the ever-changing dynamics of education.

CONCLUSION

Strategic management has been implemented based on strategic management principles even though it has not been supported by complete data so that the institution's goals have not been achieved holistically. In addition, the strategy to realize the madrasa vision is not yet supported by an organizational structure and standard operating procedures (SOP), as well as strategic planning instruments that focus on efforts to increase the competitiveness of MTsN. In particular, this research concluded

- (1) The environmental analysis carried out by the madrasah was prepared based on the principles of environmental analysis from Hunger and Wheelen, although its implementation was not yet complete due to limited resources, especially human resources for teaching staff. In environmental analysis, the madrasah has based a rational logical value system, namely based on data owned by the institution even though the database is still incomplete.
- (2) The strategic formulation in an effort to increase the competitiveness of MTsN at these two MTsNs is in accordance with the concept determined using SWOT analysis and has also formulated a vision, mission, goals, targets, strategies and policies, although not yet perfect, the excellence in these two MTsNs is supported by a value system, namely theology, which is reflected, among other things, in the qualities of monotheism, manners and morals, Islamic law, sincere values in work.
- (3) Strategic implementation at these two MTsNs has implemented the strategic management evaluation principles from Hunger & Wheelen, however, in terms of the availability of human resources, teachers are still hampered by low motivation to develop and increase the competitiveness of madrasahs.
- (4) Strategic evaluation in an effort to increase competitiveness has been carried out based on madrasah self-evaluation, but this evaluation has not been used as a guideline in efforts to increase competitiveness in a sustainable manner.

References

- 1) Adnan, A., Sujiarto, H., Iriantara, Y., & Mulianai, Y. (2022). Management of Academic Supervision to Improve Teacher Performance at MTsN 3 and MTsN 4 Banjarmasin City. *International Journal of Educational Research and Social Sciences (IJERSC)*, 3(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.51601/ijersc.v3i3.404>
- 2) Afizialhaq, M., & Sirojuddin, D. (2022). The Role of the Principal in Developing Educational Institutions in MTsN 3 Jombang. *JoEMS (Journal of Education and Management Studies)*, 5(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.32764/joems.v5i3.724>

- 3) Bahri, S. (2023). Strategies to Improve the Recruitment of New Students at MTSN 02 Lebong During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 10(9), Article 9. <https://doi.org/10.18415/ijmmu.v10i9.5050>
- 4) Bozarth, C., & Chapman, S. (1996). A contingency view of time-based competition for manufacturers. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 16(6), 56–67. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443579610119090>
- 5) Erniati Siregar, S. (2020). The Leadership Of The School In Development Quality Culture In Student Learning In Mts State 2 Medan. Dharmawangsa: *International Journal of the Social Sciences, Education and Humanitis*, 1(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.46576/ijssseh.v1i3.952>
- 6) Hariyanto, H., Wijaya, C., Yahfizham, Y. Y., & Zaini, M. F. (2021). Principal Interpersonal Communication in Decision Making and Policy Quality Improvement of MTs Ummi Lubuk Pakam. *International Journal of Educational Research and Social Sciences (IJERSC)*, 2(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.51601/ijersc.v2i1.10>
- 7) Kamal, M. F., Julianda, E., & Azhari, R. (2023). Efforts to Improve ICT-Based Learning Management Competence for Teachers of MTsN 6 Aceh Besar. *Seulanga*, 2(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.47655/seulanga.v2i1.140>
- 8) Kuthambalayan, T. S., & Bera, S. (2020). Managing product variety with mixed make-to-stock/make-to-order production strategy and guaranteed delivery time under stochastic demand. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 147, 106603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2020.106603>
- 9) Luciano, M. M., Nahrgang, J. D., & Shropshire, C. (2020). Strategic Leadership Systems: Viewing Top Management Teams and Boards of Directors from a Multiteam Systems Perspective. *Academy of Management Review*, 45(3), 675–701. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2017.0485>
- 10) Madrigal, L., Hamill, S., & Gill, D. L. (2013). Mind Over Matter: The Development of the Mental Toughness Scale (MTS). *The Sport Psychologist*, 27(1), 62–77. <https://doi.org/10.1123/tsp.27.1.62>
- 11) Meredith, J., & Akinc, U. (2007). Characterizing and structuring a new make-to-forecast production strategy. *Journal of Operations Management*, 25(3), 623–642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2006.04.006>
- 12) Meutia, M. (2021). Teacher Strategies in Improving the Quality of Students at MTs 2 Medan Country. *International Journal of Education, Social Studies, And Management (IJESSM)*, 49–57. <https://doi.org/10.52121/ijessm.v1i1.7>
- 13) Olhager, J. (2003). Strategic positioning of the order penetration point. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 85(3), 319–329. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-5273\(03\)00119-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-5273(03)00119-1)
- 14) Olhager, J., & Prajogo, D. I. (2012). The impact of manufacturing and supply chain improvement initiatives: A survey comparing make-to-order and make-to-stock firms. *Omega*, 40(2), 159–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2011.05.001>
- 15) Pujianti, E., & Sarpendi, S. (2022). The Strategy of the Head of Madrasah in Improving the Quality of Standard Input at MTS Muhammadiyah Purbolinggo East Lampung. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Konseling (JPDK)*, 4(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.31004/jpdk.v4i3.6463>
- 16) Rahman, T., Wasliman, I., Muttaqien, K., & Sauri, R. S. (2021). Accreditation Policies Implementation to Improve Performance Quality in Madrasah. *International Journal of Educational Review*, 3(2), 124–144. <https://doi.org/10.33369/ijer.v3i2.15601>
- 17) Riinawati, R. (2022). Strategy of Financing Management to Improve the Quality of Islamic Education Institution. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v14i3.1519>

- 18) Rijal, F., Nudin, B., & Samad, I. A. (2022). Islamic Religious Education Learning Innovation at the MTsN Model Banda Aceh and the MTsN Model Gandapura Bireuen. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v14i2.1930>
- 19) Rofiaty, R. (2019). The relational model of entrepreneurship and knowledge management toward innovation, strategy implementation and improving Islamic boarding school performance. *Journal of Modelling in Management*, 14(3), 662–685. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JM2-05-2018-0068>
- 20) Rosyadi, I., Aprilianto, A., & Rofiq, M. H. (2023). Development of Islamic Educational Institutions in Increasing Competitiveness in Madrasah Tsanawiyah. *Chalim Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 3(1), Article 1.
- 21) Sari, R., Murniati, M., & Bahrin, B. (2023). Madrasah Principal Management in Improving the Quality of Research Madrasahs. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 15(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v15i3.2499>
- 22) Suresmi, S., Etek, Y., Pahrudin, A., Fauzan, A., & Patimah, S. (2022). Management Of Quality Learning In A Superior Class. *Edukasi Islami: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 9(02), Article 02. <https://doi.org/10.30868/ei.v9i02.1258>
- 23) Suwandi, E. A., & Fitri, A. Z. (2023). Strategic Management Based on Cadet Education at SMAN 5 Taruna Brawijaya. *Journal of World Science*, 2(1), 12–19. <https://doi.org/10.58344/jws.v2i1.192>
- 24) Tabroni, T., Ritonga, A. H., & Us, K. A. (2023). Islamic Boarding School Management System In Increasing The Competitiveness Of Islamic Boarding Schools In Jambi Province. *International Journal of Islamic Thought and Humanities*, 2(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.54298/ijith.v2i2.130>
- 25) Widjaja, G., Supriani, Y., Badri, K. N. bin Z., Bangkara, B. M. A. S. A., & Zuhri, M. I. I. (2022). Improving the Quality of Madrasahs through Financial Management. *Nidhomul Haq : Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 7(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.31538/ndh.v7i3.2606>
- 26) Wu, X. J., Jiang, R., Tsai, J. C.-A., & Klein, G. (2023). Shared mental models in multi-team systems: Improving enterprise system implementation. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 16(2), 185–208. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMPB-05-2022-0119>
- 27) Zaid, Z. (2021). Implementation Of School Based Management To Improve The Quality Of Islamic Education At Mts Negeri 1 In Palu City. *Risalah, Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Studi Islam*, 7(2), Article 2. https://doi.org/10.31943/jurnal_risalah.v7i2.196